

Bridging Industry and Academia through Project Based Learning

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Abstract

The need to establish real synergies between the university environment and the world of work so that the student faces his academic career at the university from a business perspective, where the study of the different subjects does not represent something isolated but rather a compendium of knowledge of a holistic nature, with real and practical applicability, has led the Steam school of the European University to develop a concrete and specific academic model that has meant introducing important changes to adapt to the project-based learning methodology (PBL). This article explains the changes that have been implemented since 2012 and the implications that this has had on the teaching staff, who have had to adapt through continuous and specific training in the PBL methodology, in the adaptation of the facilities to facilitate the realization of projects, and in the relations with the business sector for collaboration in the design and development of proposals. Feedback consistently received over the years from many stakeholders, as well as from alumni after having been working for several years, leaves no doubt: project-based learning makes students engage more, learn better, and is much more effective for them to develop the set of soft skills required by companies. The three pillars on which the implementation of the PBL methodology is based, teacher training, transformation of facilities and collaboration with industry have contributed significant improvements to the academic model of the Steam School of the European University and to the way in which our students face their professional future. When project-based learning is coupled with a strong industry partnership, learning results skyrocket. Students not only acquire and master the necessary knowledge to graduate; they gradually develop the set of soft skills, such as teamwork, resilience, communication skills, and proactivity.

Keywords: Project Based Learning (PBL); Industry and University; PBL Ecosystem; Practical experience.

1 Introduction

1.1 University role

Universities are institutions of higher education, usually comprising colleges in different areas of knowledge, and with the recognized capability of granting degrees in those areas. As we know them today, universities arose in western Europe in the Middle Ages, although precursors existed in Africa and Asia in ancient times. Modern universities are an evolution of medieval schools known as “studia generalia”, which usually arose out of efforts to educate clerks and monks beyond what was addressed in the monastic schools.

In modern society, in which labour is highly specialized, universities are the institutions focused on developing knowledge and expanding the frontiers of what is known, through research, as well as on passing the existing knowledge to the new generations, through education, preparing them for the professional life [28, 33].

1.2 Drawbacks of Traditional Approaches

The role of universities in modern society is to educate and prepare new generations to be future researchers and professionals in a constantly changing society, contributing to the business world, research, and society at large [28]. However, academia and industry often lack alignment, resulting in graduates facing a gap between their education and industry expectations, especially in soft skills [29], [36].

Several drawbacks of the conventional teaching approach include:

- a) Different Atmospheres: Faculty often lack industry experience, making it difficult to prepare students for real-world environments [26].
- b) Lack of Practical Experience: While some subjects don't require industry experience, others, like Software Engineering and Supply Chain Management, benefit greatly from it [11].
- c) Lack of Project Execution: Unlike industry, academia rarely organizes activities like projects. Projects help students develop teamwork, resilience, and communication skills, which are often missing in traditional education [35].
- d) Separation of Domains: There is often a lack of communication and feedback between academia and industry, which needs to be addressed to fulfill the university's third mission [31].

1.3 The Origins of Project Based Learning at STEAM School

Project-Based Learning (PBL), based on Learning by Doing [5, 18], is widely adopted by secondary and higher education institutions [21]. Aalborg University [2, 19], a pioneer in PBL, promotes multidisciplinary project-based education, yielding better results through active student involvement [4, 24]. Since Kolb's experiential learning model [20], research and innovation in PBL have flourished [16, 32], showing positive impacts on student motivation [8, 22, 35].

PBL has been applied across various areas, subjects, and curricula. Some authors relate PBL to design thinking [12], while others use it for teaching computational thinking [15]. PBL is also used for learning agile models in Software Engineering and Design [3, 25], and non-technical subjects [30]. Many engineering schools use PBL for training future engineers, either in individual subjects or throughout the curriculum [17, 23].

The CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate) initiative complements PBL in engineering education. Adopted by over 200 schools, CDIO and PBL share the philosophy of providing practical educational experiences. CDIO focuses on developing engineering competencies through a project's life cycle, while PBL emphasizes solving complex projects that foster critical thinking and collaboration [9, 14].

At the STEAM School of Universidad Europea de Madrid (UE), the motivation in 2012 was to make students feel like engineers from day one. Traditional theoretical classes were supplemented with practical activities, but small projects rarely transcended beyond their subjects. PBL aims to offer practical learning that facilitates knowledge transfer to the professional world [16, 25, 31, 38]. However, some authors identify challenges in this transfer [8]. To address this, [7] suggests gradually introducing innovative methodologies from early courses.

In 2012, the STEAM School began its journey towards a project-based learning ecosystem [34]. This ecosystem includes practical learning in all subjects, early-year projects, integrative projects across subjects and degrees, and informal project-based learning through student clubs.

2 Pedagogical Framework. Evolution of PBL at STEAM School

2.1 The three pillars: faculty, facilities, and industry links

Throughout the last decade, the STEAM School has developed initiatives in three directions: training faculty, transforming facilities, and bridging the gap between school and industry.

Faculty Training: Training faculty in PBL methodology is essential [23, 30]. This has been achieved through specific training programs, tools for classroom use (e.g., project templates, evaluation rubrics), and periodic meetings to share best practices. Additionally, the faculty has been balanced between academic and industry professionals to use current technologies in project development.

Facility Transformation: Creating facilities that promote project work is crucial [17, 36]. This includes opening spaces for undergraduate students, involving physical and cultural changes, and modifying management practices. A workspace of over 400 square meters has been created for group projects, along with an advanced computing center with over 700 cores for real projects.

Industry Collaboration: Project-based learning is more effective with industry participation [8]. Inspired by the Triple Helix Model [6], the school has established collaboration agreements with companies as Strategic Allies and Industrial Partners. These companies participate in project design, development, and evaluation.

In summary, the methodology has been implemented through faculty training, facility transformation, and industry collaboration over the past 12 years.

2.2 12-Years Experience

During the year 2023/2024, we will celebrate the 12th anniversary of applying PBL to all degrees at our STEAM School at UE, now called Project Based School (PBS). This section describes the experience accumulated over these twelve years. The implementation of PBS has three main phases: (i) introducing projects as learning activities across several subjects, (ii) integrating projects as specific subjects in our curricula, and (iii) PBL 2.0 to enhance the methodology used by teachers.

2.2.1. Projects as Learning Activities

Each academic year, students embarked on comprehensive projects that partially covered the content of multiple courses, with various instructors contributing. These integrating projects were designed only with courses of the same year (horizontal integration), but they could belong to different quarter periods. The aims were: (i) enhance motivation and sense of belonging among students and teachers, (ii) facilitate deeper learning of specific engineering skills, (iii) develop and promote generic skills like teamwork, communication, independent learning, and effective planning, and (iv) establish a connection between the classroom and the engineering profession, enabling students to solve practical and real-world problems.

Three factors contributed to the initiative: (i) the decision made at the school's management level, (ii) a teacher training program on the methodology, and (iii) an integrated project template to align teachers and program leaders. The findings revealed promising results: increased motivation for both teachers and students, deeper understanding of specific and generic skills, and appreciation for projects involving external companies. However, areas for improvement include specialization within project groups and the need to emphasize sustainability in projects.

2.2.2. Projects as Subjects

In 2015, the school revised the PBL approach and implemented project-based courses in all undergraduate engineering programs. These courses applied knowledge from subjects taken during the same or previous academic years within practical projects. In the first year, students practiced basic engineering competencies (math, physics, programming, and business) in an "Engineering Project." In the second year, computer engineering skills were developed in a "Computer Science Project," divided into two subjects (one per semester). In the third year, the degree specialization was carried out through a "Computation Project," focusing on advanced databases, artificial intelligence, and user interfaces. No projects were conducted in the fourth year to dedicate more time to the mandatory final degree project.

Quantitative analyses from the 2021-22 academic year revealed that PBL methodology in project-focused courses provided students with experiential learning opportunities, solidifying theoretical knowledge and developing cross-cutting skills like teamwork and problem-solving. Student motivation improved, reducing dropout rates significantly. Interviews with graduates indicated enhanced competencies in teamwork, project

management, and decision-making, along with a deeper understanding of technical skills, reflected in improved pass rates in traditional subjects.

2.2.3. PBL 2.0

In the 2022/2023 academic year, we pursued three primary objectives: (i) establishing a uniform vocabulary for all teachers regarding PBL implementation, (ii) disseminating this shared vocabulary among faculty members, and (iii) providing teachers with methodological tools for effective classroom application. This ecosystem is described in the next section.

3 Project-Based Learning Ecosystem; Growing as a Learning Organization

To grow as a learning organization, a PBL ecosystem was developed at the school. Learning organizations are characterized by a true learning culture and atmosphere, where learning to learn is essential for everyone involved. They have a shared vision, which motivates collective and sustained action in a psychologically safe environment [15], [13]. The ecosystem is captured in the School's Knowledge Map.

Figure 1. School Knowledge Map. (Source: own elaboration)

The main entities in the ecosystem, centred around the School Board and the Project-Based Office, include:

1. Think Tanks: Advisory boards in higher education institutions improve curriculum, student competency development, and student interaction with the professional environment [25]. The School Board has three think tanks: the Industry Advisory Board with 22 professionals from various industries, the Academic Think Tank with 10 senior faculty members discussing internal school topics, and the Alumni Advisory Board maintaining a close link with alumni to engage with the growing community of graduates.
2. Faculty Gatherings: Communities of practice provide an enriching environment for continuous learning, professional development, and collaboration [35]. Each academic year, students carry out hundreds of projects. In July, several professors present their project organization and results to the faculty, enabling the sharing of best practices and collective learning.
3. School Awards: Awards are a proven form of motivation among students [8]. In September, the best projects in each category participate in the School Awards. Students present their artifacts or technology demonstrators, accompanied by a video showing project selection, execution, and results. Companies attend the ceremony, and their representatives vote to elect the winners.

4. European Workshop on Project-Based Learning: Every November, the school hosts the European Workshop on Project-Based Learning, facilitating external benchmarking with other European universities. Best practices, experiences, and problems are shared for continuous improvement.
5. Strategic Allies and Industrial Partners: Collaboration between universities and industry enhances innovation through knowledge exchange [1]. The school has strong relationships with industry, faculty, and facilities, forming the three pillars of the academic model. Strategic Allies are companies actively participating in program design, academic activities, facility requirements, and methodology improvement.
6. Academic Model Directorate: Within the Office of the Provost for Faculty and Research, the Academic Model Directorate establishes experiential learning academic model guidelines for the university.

The PBL Agenda is a living document composed of collectible cards that help teachers understand and implement Project-Based Learning (PBL) at the STEAM School. Each card provides concise summaries of essential information for PBL methodology. They are distributed during quarterly meetings, with new content added regularly. Key sections include motivational explanations, guidelines for project design, implementation, and assessment, recommendations, contact information for support, indicators, achieved results, phases of 'Implementing a PBL 2.0 Project,' guidelines for effective feedback, and instructions for constructing assessment rubrics. Additional cards are introduced at each quarterly faculty meeting.

4 Main Results

During these eleven years of PBL implementation in the STEAM School degrees an annual average of 30 projects based on the methodology has been generated. These projects involved an average of 12 degrees, 120 students and 65 teachers. Figure 2 shows the evolution of the number of projects in the last decade.

Figure 2. Projects per course (Source: own elaboration)

This graph shows the significant increase in the number of projects that have been carried out in the Steam School with the PBL methodology until the 2018-2019 academic year. From then on, the impact of the pandemic caused a decrease in the number of projects, data that, given the exceptional circumstances that were experienced and the difficulty of many students in regularly following classes, is considered very positive and indicative of a solid implementation of the methodology. The increase in the number of projects in the 2022-2023 academic year and the forecasts for the 2023-2024 academic year outline a scenario of growth and alignment of the subjects with the methodology.

These results highlight a fairly equitable distribution of projects in the 4 areas in which the school is structured.

Figure 3. Distribution of projects by areas (Source: own elaboration)

In 2016, the European University implemented a satisfaction survey to assess the impact that teacher training in PBL Methodology was having on the project-based learning approach carried out in the classroom. This survey has yielded values that reach 84.2% of student satisfaction, where the improvement in the solidity of learning theoretical concepts, in the development of transversal skills such as teamwork and problem solving, as well as in improving your motivation.

In addition, former students have told us about the high degree of acceptance and integration in the world of work and what they appreciate in companies that the students have developed their academic career in scenarios like those used in the business field.

On the other hand, companies have expressed their satisfaction with the APB model in two aspects, one when they participate as a jury in the UE Steam School awards where they can visualize and judge the quality and rigor of the projects and another when these students join their companies where they demonstrate their technical knowledge and “soft” skills such as teamwork, responsibility, autonomy, ease of communication, etc. I literally transfer one of the opinions linked to participation as a company jury: “I take this opportunity to thank you for your involvement in these awards which, from my point of view, are very interesting for all parties, and above all and especially for the students. Congratulations on the work and the result”

5 Conclusions and future lines of research

Feedback consistently received over the years from many stakeholders, as well as from alumni after having been working for several years, leaves no doubt: project-based learning makes students engage more, learn better, and is much more effective for them to develop the set of soft skills required by companies.

The three pillars on which the implementation of the PBL methodology is based, teacher training, transformation of facilities and collaboration with industry have contributed significant improvements to the academic model of the Steam School of the European University and to the way in which our students face their professional future.

When project-based learning is coupled with a strong industry partnership, learning results skyrocket. Students not only acquire and master the necessary knowledge to graduate; undertaking challenges and working in projects they gradually develop the set of soft skills that are so important and necessary, such as teamwork, resilience, communication skills, and proactivity.

To deliver better education, in the broadest sense of the term, project-based learning with a strong industry partnership is highly encouraged.

The future lines of research proposed by the Steam School of the European University of Madrid to improve the model are focused on the design of a continuous improvement system through the definition of a control

panel that contains KPIs that allow evaluating the degree of maturity of the implementation of the methodology and that, in addition, makes it possible to establish comparisons with other Higher Education Institutions and measure the evolution of the institution itself over time. These KPIs are also intended to provide empirical evidence on the effectiveness and impact of AI (Artificial Intelligence) in the development of PBL projects and the acquisition of learning results by students, as well as on the effectiveness and impact of PBL in the development of technical competencies on AI and in the development of a theoretical and methodological framework for the integration of AI with PBL.

In summary, the following research questions are posed: Is there a standard methodology that identifies how to implement a continuous quality cycle in the implementation of PBL in higher education institutions? If not, how could it be defined? On the other hand, what impact do new AI tools have on the development of PBL? Does PBL help to avoid the risks of LLMs regarding authorship of works? Is PBL a good tool for teaching the use of AI tools?

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